

Online Class Observation of the School of Education College Instructors: Teaching and Learning Engagement

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ABSTRACT

Online class observations of the School of Education (SED) college instructor's teaching, provide a panoramic view as to what is happening in the virtual classroom and how teaching and learning engagements are maximized by the instructors and the students. This study featured the result on the evaluation of the teaching performance of the SED college instructors utilizing the PAASCU flexible learning evaluation form for online/virtual classroom observation. Sixteen fulltime and part-time faculty were observed virtually in their classes through the Google Meet. Observations revealed that the SED faculty performed excellently in their teaching, exhibiting the lecture method using PowerPoint presentation as the predominant teaching strategy. It was further observed that teaching and learning engagements indicated three types, namely: cognitive, behavioral, and affective/emotional engagements. These are evidently manifested when teacher gives lectures, teacher asks questions, teacher gives directions, teacher demonstrates, and teacher praises/encourages. Succinctly, observation of classes online shows promises of a new hybrid model of teaching strategy and engagements in the academe.

Subject Area

Teaching and Learning Evaluation

Keywords: *Online/Virtual Class Observation, Teaching, Learning Engagements*

INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented disruption brought about by COVID 19 in the educational terrain compelled schools to adopt the flexible teaching-learning classroom instruction through online classes. Evading the spread of the virus, schools have to hold classes virtually; hence class

observations are also done virtually. Accordingly, the herculean challenge is how to keep on with the instructional process stepping aside the face-to-face teaching and learning. The paradigm shifts from the face-to-face instruction, where students and instructors indulged in classroom discourse, classroom interactions and actual classroom activities, are replaced with the online teaching and learning modalities. In many ways, the online classroom mirrors the physical classroom, where the students need to be able to see and hear the teacher and other students, and have a good view of the board and their own learning materials.

In a virtual classroom the student can see and hear the teacher through the video/audio stream. It allows teachers and students to connect online in real time. Virtual classrooms utilize video conferencing, online whiteboards and screen sharing to allow educators to hold live lectures, virtual office hours, and discussions with students in an interactive setting. Virtual classrooms are meant to replicate the experience of physical classrooms, with the added benefits of file sharing, instant feedback and interaction, and are ideal in distance learning situations (Li & Lalani, 2020).

Class observation for college instructors at San Isidro College, School of Education (SED) is a periodic exercise done by the dean to help evaluate the teaching performance and students' learning. It is a part of a formal job performance evaluation done at a regular schedule every semester. Evaluation is a continuous process that helps to monitor instruction and check on the progress of students' learning from time to time. It also provides valuable feedback on what transpired in the classroom and on how teachers and students manage to navigate the educational environment.

With the coming accreditation of the School of Education, the assessment of classroom instruction is one relevant indicator for quality assurance. Observing the teachers' way of handling their classes is done every semester following some guidelines/criteria. With the pandemic, the best option to resume classes is to have this done virtually. Hence, it follows that the class observations done by the dean are also done virtually. The schedules of class observations are plotted in a matrix to avoid conflict in the observation's date and time for both the observer and the instructors. Once the teacher opted for a particular schedule, the invitation and the link is sent to the dean to be able to join the class via the Google Meet,

This study aimed to evaluate the SED College instructors' teaching performance as they deliver their lessons via the Google Meet. The result of the evaluation could provide evidences of monitoring and evaluating the instructors in their teaching as well as on the learning performance of the students. Teacher and students' interactions are also observed in their teaching and learning engagements during the academic exercise.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study is anchored on the premise that classroom observations done by the dean, chair, or head of schools is one facet that measures quality assurance in the academe. Classroom observations are a quantitative and qualitative way of recording and measuring the teacher's behavior and mastery by systematically watching and recording them in action (Torsh, (2019). Effective and efficient teachings of teachers mirror the kind of performance of the students. It could reflect the way teachers motivate and inspire their learners to become engaged in their lesson or the subject they taught.

Traditionally, classroom observations are done in a face-to-face manner. Even before COVID 19, the ubiquity of the new technology causes the burgeoning of the use of smartphones, laptops, computers and gadgets to aid and facilitate instruction. The integration of ICT in the presentation of lessons becomes trending. With the sudden change and shift away from the classroom due to the pandemic, high growth and adoption of the new technology allowed classes to resume through online platforms. This move was unplanned and unprepared, with no sufficient training for teachers and students, poor internet bandwidth and connectivity, poor user experience, and other technology problems. However, despite these challenges, classes have to continue and schools have to move forward. Since classes are resumed, class observations are also done.

The Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU, 2021) has developed an evaluation form for classes recited virtually. This is the instrument used in this study. There are five indicators used as the criteria to evaluate the teaching performance of college instructors. Figure 1 illustrates the criteria for flexible learning evaluation for online/virtual classroom observation in the first box. The result of the observation would show the online teaching strategies used by the college instructors as well as the teaching and learning engagement of the teacher and the students, as reflected in the second box.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram

The criteria on *Learning Outcomes* measures whether the module's Intended Learning Outcomes are clearly stated and are aligned with the Course Learning Outcomes. It sees to it that the structure and plan of the day's virtual class and the expected output/expected outcome/s is/are clearly stated.

The criteria on *Instructional Content and Delivery* check as to whether the instructional materials (content) represent up-to-date theory and practice in the discipline, and contribute to the attainment of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO). It checks if the instructional materials are presented in a variety of ways (lecture, text readings, video, etc.) in order to engage the students and encourage them to connect to the content. It further checks if the Learning Management System (LMS) or technology's features were optimized for effective teaching-learning process.

The criteria on *Instructor's Presence and Support* sees to it that the instructor's support is manifested in giving feedback, rejoinders, comments, response to queries, suggestions and clarificatory questions and in providing scaffolded directions for the activities. It also looks into whether the instructor's presence is felt by guiding the students to attain the intended learning

outcomes through encouraging and monitoring them to perform and move or progress towards the attainment of the intended learning outcomes until the end of the class.

The criteria on *Learning Experience and Interaction* assesses whether the learning experiences offered to students are relevant and promote the attainment of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO). It also checks if the learning experiences are varied and promote high student engagement or participation; and whether the learning activities and tasks provide opportunities for peer interaction and self-directed learning.

The criteria on *Assessment* measures whether these assessments are clearly aligned to the Intended Learning Outcomes and seeks evidence to assess the attainment of the ILO. It further checks if specific descriptive criteria (such as a rubrics) are provided so that the students are guided in achieving the intended outcomes of the assessments which is also used by the instructor in evaluating the students' outcomes/outputs or performance. It also checks whether students are provided with multiple opportunities to receive feedback at appropriate times to track learning. The five criteria for flexible online learning aim to engage both teachers and students in the teaching and learning process.

Engagement in the classroom entails a strong relationship between the student and the teacher. Engagement is the necessary first step for learning (Cavanagh, 2019). Teacher-student engagement is a key element of a positive school climate, with a large body of research linking it to academic achievement. The term *engagement* can provide an overarching framework for many positive individual processes, relationships within the school, and contextual qualities (Axelson & Flick, 2010).

Engagement in the classroom falls within three categories: *behavioral*, *cognitive*, and *affective* (Fredericks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). These three types are distinct yet interrelated. *Behavioral engagement* conveys the presence of general "on-task behavior." This entails effort and persistence along with paying attention, asking questions, seeking help that enables one to accomplish the task at hand, and not disrupting instruction. It is the observable act of students being involved in learning. *Cognitive engagement* connotes investment aimed at comprehending complex concepts and issues and acquiring difficult skills. It conveys deep (rather than surface-level) processing of information whereby students gain a critical or higher-order understanding of the subject matter and solve challenging problems. Cognitively engaged students often go beyond the requirements because they enjoy being challenged. *Affective/Emotional engagement* connotes emotional reactions linked to task investment. The greater the student's interest level, enjoyment, positive attitude, the positive value held, curiosity, and a sense of belonging (and the less the anxiety, sadness, stress, and boredom), the greater the affective engagement. Based on current research and understanding, one could not specify how these three types of engagement interact, and it is not certain which antecedents are linked to which types" (Ladd & Dinella, 2009). Affective/emotional state can impact levels of engagement. Trauma affects students' executive functioning and self-regulation skills. This means they will have a harder time planning, remembering, and focusing on what they need to learn (Imad, 2020).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study assessed and analyzed the online class observation results of the SED college instructors at San Isidro College during the second semester of AY 2020-2021. Specifically, it answered the questions on:

1. What is the evaluation of the SED college instructors' teaching performance based on the flexible online class observation criteria on:
 - 1.1. Learning Outcomes;
 - 1.2. Instructional content and delivery;
 - 1.3. Instructor's presence and support;
 - 1.4. Learning Experience and Interaction; and
 - 1.5. Assessment?
2. What teaching strategies are demonstrated by the SED college instructors in their online class?
3. What teaching and learning engagements are manifested during the online class?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design employing qualitative analysis based from the result of actual class observations done to 16 (70%) SED college instructors teaching the different fields of specializations. The School of Education at San Isidro College served as the research locale where the classroom observations occurred.

San Isidro College (SIC) was founded by the late Fr. Joseph Reith, S.J., a Jesuit Missionary in July 1949. The College was named after the town's patron saint, San Isidro Labrador, bearing the motto "*Ora et labora*" which means "prayer and work". It is the only Catholic institution of higher learning in Malaybalay, and the oldest in the province. SIC is duly accredited by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd). It is also a member of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP) and the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS). From its humble beginnings, the school continues to provide quality Catholic Education where students adhere to its philosophy, vision, mission, goals and objectives, core values and graduate attributes.

During the second semester of the academic year 2020-2021, there were a total of twenty-three faculty members, six of whom have full-time status and the rest have part-time status. Majority of these part-timers are full-time teachers in the elementary and senior high of the Integrated Basic Education group. The 2nd semester of the academic year 2020-2021 showed that SED's enrolment of the college students totaled to 151, where 78 are from the BEED and 73 from the BSED spread across the different major fields.

The major instrument used for the online class observation is PAASCU's flexible learning evaluation form for online/virtual classroom observation containing 5 major criteria, namely: *Learning Outcome* with two statements reflecting the intended learning outcomes and the expected output/outcome. The second criterion is on *Instructional Content & Delivery* with three statements underscoring the instructional materials and the learning management system. The third criterion is on *Instructor's presence & support* with two statements accentuating how the teacher's presence and support are evident. The fourth criterion is on *Learning Experience & Interaction* with three

statements highlighting of students' engagement of the lesson and participation in class. The fifth criterion is on *Assessment* with three statements related to evaluating students' performance. There is also a space for narrative comments, suggestions and recommendations for the observed teacher to provide for qualitative inputs on what were observed. A 5-point Likert scale evaluates the class observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of Teaching Performance

Table 1 shows the result of the evaluation of teaching performance based on the criteria set by PAASCU on flexible learning.

Table 1. Evaluation on the online observation based on the criteria for flexible learning

A. Learning Outcomes	Rating	Description
1. The module's Intended Learning Outcomes are clearly stated and are aligned with the Course Learning Outcomes.	4.88	Excellent
2. The structure and plan of the day's virtual class and the expected output/expected outcome/s is/are clearly stated.	4.75	Excellent
Sub-Total Average	4.82	Excellent
B. Instructional Content and Delivery		
1. The instructional materials (content) represent up-to-date theory and practice in the discipline, and contribute to the attainment of the Intended Learning Outcomes.	4.94	Excellent
2. The instructional materials are presented in a variety of ways (lecture, text readings, video, etc.) in order to engage the students and encourage them to connect to the content.	4.75	Excellent
3. The Learning Management System or technology's features were optimized for effective teaching-learning process.	4.56	Excellent
Sub-Total Average	4.75	Excellent
C. Instructor's Presence and Support		
1. The instructor's support is manifested in giving feedback, rejoinders, comments, response to queries, suggestions and clarificatory questions and in providing scaffolded directions for the activities.	4.75	Excellent
2. The instructor's presence is felt by guiding the students to attain the intended learning outcomes through encouraging and monitoring them to perform and move or progress towards the attainment of the intended learning outcomes until the end of the class.	4.75	Excellent
Sub-Total Average	4.75	Excellent
D. Learning Experience and Interaction		
1. The learning experiences offered to students are relevant and promote the attainment of the Intended Learning Outcomes.	4.88	Excellent
2. The learning experiences are varied and promote high student engagement or Participation.	4.44	Excellent
3. The learning activities and tasks provide opportunities for peer interaction and self-directed learning.	4.50	Excellent
Sub-Total Average	4.61	Excellent
E. Assessment		
1. The assessments are clearly aligned to the Intended Learning Outcomes and seek evidence to assess the attainment of the ILO.	4.12	Very Good
2. Specific descriptive criteria (such as a rubrics) are provided so the students are guided in achieving the intended outcomes of the assessments which is also used by the instructor in evaluating the students' outcomes/outputs or performance.	3.88	Very Good
3. Students are provided with multiple opportunities to receive feedback at appropriate times to track learning.	4.00	Very Good
Sub-Total Average	4.00	Very Good
OVERALL	4.59	Excellent

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The results of the class observations indicate that the criteria in *Learning Outcomes*, *Instructional content and delivery*, *Instructor's presence and support*, and *Learning Experience and interaction* manifested an excellent rating. This means that the college instructors in the School of Education delivered their lessons excellently in these criteria. The *assessment* criterion however was rated as *very good*. The overall rating for the criteria showed that these were excellently demonstrated by the SED college instructors.

Taking into account the ratings of the individual instructors, they generally performed excellently in their teaching. The instructors have prepared well in presenting their lessons especially that the class observation was scheduled, owing to the fact that they have to invite the dean and send the link of their Google Meet classes. The instructors have prepared their PowerPoint presentations and other forms of presentations like video clips, music, art, pictures, and other authentic materials. These teaching paraphernalia enhanced their presentation and kept the students engaged in their classes. Table 2 shows the ratings of individual college instructors in their online classes observed.

Table 2. Results of Instructor's Teaching Observation based on the criteria set by PAASCU

Teacher	Learning Outcome	Instructional Content & Delivery	Instructor's presence & support	Learning Experience & Interaction	Assessment	Average
T-1	4.50	4.30	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.57
T-2	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.67
T-3	4.50	4.67	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.50
T-4	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.33	4.27
T-5	4.50	4.67	5.00	4.33	4.33	4.57
T-6	4.50	4.33	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.43
T-7	4.50	4.67	3.50	3.67	3.67	4.00
T-8	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.80
T-9	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.33	4.00	4.47
T-10	5.00	4.67	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.73
T-11	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.80
T-12	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.80
T-13	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	3.33	4.67
T-14	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.33	4.33	4.53
T-15	4.50	4.67	5.00	4.67	4.00	4.57
T-16	5.00	4.33	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.53

Legend: 5 4.20-5.00 Excellent (E) 2 1.80-2.59 Fair (F) T-1 to T-16 Teachers Observed
 4 3.40-4.19 Very Good (VG) 1 1.00-1.79 Poor (P)
 3 2.60-3.39 Good (G)

Teaching Strategies used

Matrix 1 reflects the strategies utilized by the college instructors during their virtual lessons. All the lessons of the SED faculty were done via the Google Meet class. As observed, the teachers followed a kind of routine activity where they have the *preparatory phase*, the *lesson proper phase*, and the *closing phase*. In the preparatory phase, the teacher greeted the class, checked the attendance, have the prayers said, reviewed the previous lesson, and introduced the objectives of the new lesson. These activities are typically considered as very logical in opening the lesson. In the *lesson proper phase*, the teacher introduced the topic/s and usually presented the lecture using

PowerPoint slides, video clips, actual demonstration, discussion, and other ways of presentations. Technology played a very important role in the online class, and this requires teachers and students to be familiar with their gadgets in order to be attuned with their classes. The predominant strategies are the lecture, discussion and demonstration coupled with other strategies. *In the closing phase* the teacher usually asked the students to recapitulate on what was learned, gave assignments/work activities, ended with a closing prayer, and bade goodbye to the students.

Matrix 1. Teaching Strategies Demonstrated by the SED College Instructors during the online class observation.

Teachers Observed	Teaching Strategies observed during the class observation via Google Meet
T-1	-Lecture using video clips -Audio listening to musical pieces of different music composition
T-2	-Lecture-discussion method using PowerPoint presentation online -Story presentation
T-3	-Lecture-discussion using whiteboard presentation online -Demonstration of activity with set criteria
T-4	-Lecture presentation through art interpretation
T-5	-Lecture using PowerPoint presentation and video clip -Lecture-Discussion
T-6	-Student group reporting using PowerPoint online with teacher's guidance
T-7	-Lecture method using PowerPoint presentation online -Use of pictures
T-8	-Lecture-Discussion-Demonstration using PPT presentation online -use of drawings of chains -Chat quiz time; Q&A
T-9	-Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint online -Use of examples
T-10	-Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation and video presentation -student activity online
T-11	-Lecture-discussion integrated with various presentations e.g. slides, video clips, stories -motivational lecture
T-12	-Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation online -sharing ideas and reflections
T-13	-Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation -use of stories and narratives
T-14	-Lecture using PowerPoint presentation
T-15	-Lecture discussion using the lyrics of the song -Oral recitation of students
T-16	-Lecture using PowerPoint presentation online -Discussion; Q&A

The teaching strategies utilized by teachers in their online teaching are basically the lecture method. The lecture method is a versatile way of teaching as teachers gives a direct influence to the learners. With the lecture method, the teacher becomes eclectic in their presentation since they utilized the lecture with the PowerPoint presentation, lecture-discussion, lecture-demonstration, lecture using creative techniques on songs, music, stories, narratives, games, video clips, picture illustrations, art work, authentic materials, and even reporting. From the observations, teachers generally present their lecture using the PowerPoint slides, explaining and discussing what are written in the slides. This strategy allows the teacher to elaborate the topic and could ask the

students to contribute and participate in the discussion when the teacher calls on them to recite or respond to her questions.

The lecture method provides information to the students. When teachers lecture in class, they clarify and explain the concepts and the topics discussed. Lecturing to the whole class saves time on the part of the teacher and the learners. It is important that teachers communicate clearly for students to understand the lesson. With classes recited online, it is important that teachers provide interesting and not too long lectures to avoid boredom of the students (Study Quirks, 2010).

One flaw with the virtual class is that the whole body view of the teacher is not often featured. Many times, only the slides are visible and the voice of the teacher, making the eye-to-eye contact between the teacher and the students practically missing. The body language portion is missing. It becomes impersonal. Even the students are not visible because they only project their profile picture, unless the teacher would ask them to open their cameras. Usually, they do not open their cameras because they would need to have the load for their device and some of them have poor internet connectivity. Then there is the possibility of students not really concentrating on the lecture because they could not be monitored by the teachers anyway. The holding power of the teacher and the kind of motivation the teacher exhibits could keep the students engaged in the lecture or learning activities. It is very important that the teacher knows how to sustain the engagement of the students in the activities that the teachers prepared for them.

With the virtual classroom, the teacher has very limited way of knowing if the students really attended the class or if they really learned what was given in the lecture. Students can “leave” the room anytime they want and could refrain from responding to the teacher’s questions. Based from the class observations however, teachers have their coping strategies to keep the students engaged in their lesson by constantly calling on them to participate. The teacher constantly checks on the presence of the students and in this way, the students are alerted that their teacher is monitoring their presence. Small class size is advantageous because all the students are given the opportunity to participate in the discussion even if their responses are not really substantial. As observed, the teachers show appreciation and acknowledges students’ responses, giving them the confidence to participate.

Teachers who prepared work activities for their students during and after the lectures usually engaged their students to participate and get involved in the learning process. The cooperative group-work activity done by the students allow them to collaborate and discuss among themselves how to go about their assigned task. This is a good opportunity for the teacher to encourage and motivate the students to sustain their engagement in the lesson. Some teachers allow some time for the students to work collaboratively and then after some time, they would come back to their virtual class and report on their output. In this teaching style, there is more student interaction since the students take turns in reporting and presenting their outputs. The cognitivist approach in teaching and learning becomes evident online.

Matrix 2 shows the summary of class observation of the SED faculty, generally reflecting the topic of the lesson, preparatory phase, lesson proper phase, and closing phase, and the teaching strategies used.

Matrix 2. Summary of class observations of the SED College Instructor's teaching presentation

Teachers Observed	Teaching Strategies observed during the class observation via Google Meet
T-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic: <i>Music Appreciation</i> • Preparatory Phase: Teacher greeted the class and proceeded with her lesson. She presented the video clip of Celine Dion on <i>All by Myself</i> and asked the students why Celine stopped in her singing as some point. She gave a brief story on the background of the music and why Celine stopped singing. She then gave a brief lecture on classical music on types of musical expression, rhythmic expression, lyrics over the music, and the way performers express themselves. • Lesson Proper Phase: Teacher presented one video clip of another composition and asked the students the movement of the music. Every time she presents a video clip of the composition she asked the student their observations of the flow of the music, in terms of movement, tempo, notes played, expression. This she did with <i>Lyra angelica, Chopin's, Nutcracker, The hole of the mountain king, Chopin's ballad' etc.</i> The teacher asked the students to listen, observed, and gave their analysis of the composition played based from her lecture. She usually gave the background of the music and narrates stories associated with these music. The stories are entertaining and it could elicit interest in the learners. • Closing Phase: At the end of her lecture and presentations of video clips, she asked the students if they understood the lesson. She also asked for clarificatory questions. Finding no questions, she ended the class by saying goodbye. • Teaching Strategy: <i>Lecture using video clips of compositions and audio listening to musical pieces of different compositions</i>
T-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic: <i>Literary Technique</i> • Preparatory Phase: Teacher presented the objectives of the lesson. She reviewed the story of <i>the Wall</i> by giving a brief summary. • Lesson Proper Phase: She presented the story of <i>the Lovers</i>. She gave them 6 questions to answer in relation to the story. Students were called to respond. Some wrote their responses in the chat box and the teacher read their responses. She asked them questions for analyzing literary techniques. First, by asking the protagonist of the story; the characterization; the climax; the foreshadowing; the third person omniscient point of view; and the last on identifying if the story is a legend, a folktale or a romance. • Closing Phase: For their assignment the students will work in groups to give the summary of <i>The Lover</i>. They will form an illustration or a diagram or a flow chart about the story. The teacher will give the rubric for assessment and the assignment will be submitted next meeting. Another assignment is to write a 300-word essay to analyze Head's story. The activity that they will do will be discussed next meeting. At the end of the lesson the students were made to do a recapitulation of the lessons learned. • Teaching Strategy: <i>Online Lecture-discussion method using PPT</i>
T-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic- <i>Palitang Turo- Minamasid</i> • Preparatory Phase: Teacher started the lesson with a prayer led by a student in Filipino. Teacher provided a brief review of the previous lesson. • Lesson Proper Phase: She presented the lesson on "<i>hagdang karanasan- Minamasid</i>" using the white board. She provided activity for the students and gave them 10 minutes to work on this then giving the criteria for rating them. After 10 minutes she asked them to present what they did. This was an interactive activity with the students. • Closing Phase: Then, before the end of classes she said she will post the assignment in their Google classroom • Teaching Strategy: <i>Lecture-Discussion using the whiteboard online</i>

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- T-4
- **Topic:** *Ch.4 - Subject of Art*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher requested a student to lead the prayer. The objectives were presented. Teacher presented in the screen 3 picture paintings and asked the students to give their analysis and share this to the class. Students were called to give their analysis. The teacher has a very pleasant disposition.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** The teacher gave the lecture on *subject of an art* and *types of subject of an art*. After her lecture she again brought out the same pictures and let the students analyze the pictures according to its *subject as an art* and the *types of subject of an art*. She appreciated the students for their responses. Then, she asked them to interpret the pictures by selecting their preference and giving why they choose the particular picture. After the students have done their analysis of the paintings the teacher asked them if they understood their lesson.
 - **Closing Phase:** The teacher reminded them that she will post the lesson and the work activity in the Google classroom before they are dismissed. She thanked everyone for their participation and bade everyone goodbye.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture-discussion using pictures/paintings and PowerPoint presentation online*
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- T-5
- **Topic:** *What is the difference between moral and ethics?*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher greeted the class and let a student led the prayer. There was a recapitulation of the previous lesson and the teacher presented a news article on the Genovese murder case. She asked the students to give their opinion about the case and the students responded well.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** She presented the topic of the day on the 2 philosophical theories: Teleological and Deontological. She presented the lesson using PowerPoint presentation. As she lectured she also gave example stories and cases to illustrate her lecture. She lectured on ethical egotism, characteristics of utilitarianism, and finally on Deontology ethics and Kant's theory. She gave examples that students can understand.
 - **Closing Phase:** At the end of her lecture she told the class that she will post their activity in the Google classroom. Then, she bade goodbye to the class, just as the class bade farewell to her, too.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture method using PowerPoint online*
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- T-6
- **Topic:** *Lecture Method*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** The lesson was a video recording because the actual time schedule did not push through. The teacher asked the students to have group-reporting on the topic on *Lecture Method*. There was more of student-talk than teacher-talk when class interaction is concerned because the student did the lecturing and the discussion. The teacher merely served as a facilitator of learning-- elaborating and enhancing the student's lecture/report.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** The student's report was presented in a PowerPoint and every time the reporter could not explain the topic, the teacher elucidated this. There were many subtopics related to lecture method that was reported by the student who seems to be the leader of the group. The other short topics were read by the other reporters from the PowerPoint and the teacher did the explaining. It seems that most of the interactions were done by the teacher and the reporter. Later, the teacher asked the class some questions for them to interact as well. Since most of the students cannot give their verbal response, the teacher allowed them to write their answers in the chat box and he just read these to the class. Two groups of reporters have finished their topics.
 - **Closing Phase:** After the reports were done the teacher gave them instructions on their requirements for the class. Before the closing prayer, the teacher reminded the students to visit their chat box for any concerns and questions. Prayer was said before adjournment
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Student Reporting with teacher as facilitator using PowerPoint presentation online*
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- T-7
- **Topic-** *Balitang Isports*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher started the class with a prayer led by a student in Filipino. She gave a review of the lesson on *Lathalain (feature writing)*. However, the student seems to forget what their lesson was all about, so the teacher did the recap of the previous lesson. After the review the teacher presented the objectives of the new lesson on *Balitang Isports*.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** During the presentation, the teacher showed through the screen pictures of sports personality like Manny Pacquiao, Rafael Nepomoceno, etc (8 persons) then asked the students to identify them and give the sports they are famous of. This is a good way to keep the students engaged however the students do not know many of these sports personality, so the teacher have to do the identifying. It could have been better if the teacher assigned the students ahead of time to make a research of a sports personality and then present these to class during their meeting. After the motivation, the teacher presented the lesson on the parts of sports news and how to write one. She read some samples of sports news highlighting on what this part of the news is. After the lesson presentation, she asked if the students have questions. She then asked each one to give their favorite sports and to write a news about this. However, she did not let them write the new right there in their class, instead she dismisses them and make this activity as their assignment
 - **Closing Phase:** She has still some remaining time but the class was dismissed. She could have given them more questions to respond interactively or she could have given them a quiz to check if they understood the lesson. Since she assigned them to write a sports news, she should expect that they will be able to report these next meeting
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture method using PowerPoint online*
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- T-8
- **Topic:** *Proteins and Amino Acids*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher reviewed the lesson on Carbohydrates by asking review questions linking these to the new topic.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** She presented the new lesson on proteins and amino acids asking the students what are proteins and what is amino acid, as her motivating questions. She is very clear and articulate in her manner of presenting the lesson. She presents the functions of proteins, amino acids, acid base properties, zwitterions, classification of amino acids, etc. Aside from the pictures and illustrations of these using the PowerPoint, she also draws illustrations in the whiteboard to make her point clear. Her manner of presenting is very clear and the students could understand her because they could answer her questions. She has a way of engaging her students to respond by giving them time allotment. Her aura is such that she could engage the students to respond.
 - **Closing Phase:** Before she ended her class the teacher asked if the students have questions and clarifications calling them one-by-one until everyone was called. This is good because it could serve as attendance check whether the students really finished their class lesson. She thanked them for their participation. Closing prayer was said by the student before they bade goodbye to each one. The teacher thanked everyone for their participation.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture-discussion-demonstration using PPT presentation online*
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- T-9
- **Topic:** *Building a People, building a nation*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher presented a PPT lecture starting with a prayer led by the student, then the objectives, then a motivation question on why do we need to build a people and build a nation?
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** She presented her lecture through the PowerPoint, read the lecture then explain/discuss. To involve the students in the learning process, she let the students read the PowerPoint notes and the teacher explained and discussed giving examples to illustrate. She continued with this method of letting the students read the slides and teacher explains. The topics moved to the *Preamble of the Philippines* as the
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	<p>bases for building the character of the people, then moved to the topic on the strengths of the Filipino in terms of its value system, then the weaknesses of the Filipinos. She asked the students to give examples of their experiences illustrating strengths and weaknesses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Closing Phase: To end her lecture and discussion, she asked the students whether they understood the lesson. She also asked them to make an assessment on what they have learned by making a report to show evidences on how Filipinos show strengths and weaknesses in their value system and its effects to the community• Teaching Strategy: <i>Lecture discussion using PowerPoint online</i>
T-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Topic: <i>Module on Game-based Learning (Fraction)</i>• Preparatory Phase: Teacher greeted and welcomed her students warmly. She led them in prayer, then, presented the objectives of the lesson. The teacher is articulate in her presentation and she has a positive aura.• Lesson Proper Phase: She presented a video on how to facilitate a game based strategy however; this did not work out well, so she needed someone to help her out. Later when the video was already functioning, it shows the top 10 fun games that could be utilized in Mathematics. This was presented twice for students to really get through the games. She let them work on an activity where they will have to answer 3 questions posted by the teacher. She gave them time to do this. Once they were done, the teacher asked them to give their answers for the 3 questions. She acknowledged and appreciated their responses. She then gave them an assessment tasks to work in pairs. The task is to develop a mathematical game that has instructional value following the template. The students will select from the top 10 games presented and she gave them instructions on what to do using a topic from Fractions.• Closing Phase: She asked that these will be their assignment next meeting after they have already their partner. It was evident that the students were engaged in the discussion. The teacher was very convivial to the students and the students appreciated her such that the one who led the prayer even included her in the prayer. The teacher thanked everyone before they bade goodbye.• Teaching Strategy: <i>Lecture discussion using PowerPoint and video presentations, coupled with student activity online; Think-Pair-Share</i>
T-11	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Topic: <i>Building and Enhancing New Literacies across the curriculum- Creativity Literacy</i>• Preparatory Phase: Teacher greeted the class joyfully and had their prayer presented in a video clip. After the prayer, she again greeted the class with mirth. It is observed that the teacher radiates enthusiasm in her teaching. She asked the students to give a recap of their previous lesson which was also responded well by the students• Lesson Proper Phase: She presented the new lesson on building and enhancing creativity and she did these with several presentations like: video clip, PPT slide, song lyrics; pictures, synopsis of a movie clip, asking questions for students to respond verbally and in their chat box, a mini-debate, etc. Obviously the teacher engaged her students actively to sustain their interest. Her initial motivation question is “<i>Are you creative?</i>” Most of the students responded “<i>Maybe</i>”. This same question was her ending query before she dismissed the class. She also asked the students to make a mini-debate on whether “<i>creativity is learned or inherited?</i>”. She presented her lecture using PPT slide and discussed the topic extensively.• Closing Phase: At the end of her lecture, she asked the students to give a wrap-up/summary on what they have learned. Then, she asked again the question <i>Are you creative?</i> This time most of the responses were “<i>Yes</i>”. The lesson was successfully recited. Teacher put much effort in presenting her lessons interestingly for the students to be engaged in the presentations. Lesson preparation is evident. The teacher is indeed very creative!• Teaching Strategy: <i>Online Lecture discussion integrated with various presentations like slides, video clips, stories, etc.</i>

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- T-12
- **Topic:** *Technology age*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** The teacher started the class with a prayer led by a student. He presented the objectives of the lesson. The teacher has a pleasant and convivial personality adding life and zest to his presentation. He is very interactive with the students who also have caught the fever of his enthusiasm. Aside from the verbal interaction of the students he also encouraged the shy ones to write their answers in the chat box and read these.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** The lesson for the day was presented through a PowerPoint presentation. As the lecture progresses, the teacher stays connected with the class by asking them to share their ideas. He posted reflection questions that allow the students to think and give their ideas. The topic was interestingly discussed and the students were given the opportunity to reflect and discuss their ideas and opinions.
 - **Closing Phase:** At the end of the lecture discussion the teacher gave time to entertain students' questions. He also gave announcements and reminders regarding their work activities and assured them to send the links that they will need for their assignment. Finally, he gave them topics in advance for readings and research for their next lesson thus preparing them for discussion.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture-discussion method using PowerPoint presentations and question and answer on line*
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- T-13
- **Topic-** *El Filibusterismo*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Prayer was said. Then the teacher gave a review of the previous lesson by asking the students to discuss/describe their picture/representations about *Noli Me Tangere*. The students were interactive during this review lesson.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** The teacher presented the new lesson on *El Filibusterismo* which is a sequel of *Noli*. As she presented the lesson she told the excerpts of the stories and asked questions on why Rizal wrote the novel in another country; what are Rizal's experiences; what were his objectives in writing the novels; etc. Interaction between the teacher and the students was evident. The teacher appreciated the students for their responses.
 - **Closing Phase:** She gave students assignment to view the movie of Rizal and posted some questions for students to work on. She provided the link and guide for the movie. Based from the lecture, the teacher's assignment reinforces the lesson.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation coupled with stories and narratives*
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- T-14
- **Topic:** *Sampling and sampling procedure*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** The teacher presented the topics clearly and provided example on what he reads from the PPT.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** He continued to discuss about the topic, giving some examples where they could apply what was lectured. The teacher asked on whether the student understood the lecture as presented in the PowerPoint. All the topics were discussed and explained very well by the teacher based from the slides on the ppt. After the topics were discussed the teacher asked if the students have queries.
 - **Closing Phase:** Since there were no questions from the students the teacher informed that they will have a quiz to check if they understood the lecture. He will post the quiz in the Google classroom as well as the lecture presentation. The class was dismissed for them to start answering their quiz.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture Method using PowerPoint presentation online*
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- T-15
- **Topic:** *Ang Huling El Bimbo*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** Teacher requested a student to lead a prayer in Filipino. She greeted them and asked them how they are. She gave a review of the song they took up last meeting and this was done briefly,
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** She presented the new song the *El Bimbo* with its lyrics. It serves both as a motivation and the presentation of the lesson. The teacher asked the students questions related to the song like “*Sino ang inspirasyong sa kanta? ano ang ipinahiwatig ng kanta? Bakit sumikat and kantang ito?* She called the students to respond to her questions to encourage them to participate. Then she asked the students to choose a line or a stanza from the lyrics of the song as to what struck them. She gave them time to think and after which gave the oral recitation one by one. She thanked the students for their participation and involvement in the discussion. She asked her final question as to what the music wants to convey to our culture and problems in society.
 - **Closing Phase:** At the end of the lesson the teacher said she will post the activity in the Google classroom. She thanked everyone and bade farewell. The closing prayer was done and reminded everyone to stay safe.
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture-discussion using the lyrics of the song online*
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- T-16
- **Topic:** *Physical Fitness and Misconceptions related to it*
 - **Preparatory Phase:** The teacher started with a prayer then greeted her students. She made use of the PowerPoint presentation although there was a slight problem with the technology. The teacher is enthusiastic to present her lecture.
 - **Lesson Proper Phase:** She presented the lesson on physical fitness and the misconceptions related to these. She read from the lecture in the slides then gave examples every time she has examples. Usually she gave real-life experiences as examples. After her lecture she asked the students questions and called them one by one. Generally, students responded in the dialect and the teacher is contented that they were able to answer and participate in the discussion. Everyone was called to recite. The lecture lasted for one hour and the remaining 30 minutes was for the question and answer regarding the lecture.
 - **Closing Phase:** After the lesson, the teacher gave announcements and reminders particularly on the answers to the modules that they have; to submit these to the guard to keep themselves constantly safe. Prayers were recited then she bade goodbye to the class
 - **Teaching Strategy:** *Lecture using PowerPoint online*
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Teaching and Learning Engagements

Matrix 3 shows the teaching and learning engagement of the teacher and students in the online class. Typically, the teacher has to show the teaching engagement to allow the students to capture the enthusiasm that they radiate to their students, and thereby allowing the students to be engaged in the learning process. Teaching and learning engagement of the teachers and the students could be described as *cognitive engagement, behavioral engagement, and affective/emotional engagement* (Fredericks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004).

From the observations of the SED faculty’s classes, the teaching engagement observed included: *teacher lectures, teacher asks questions, teacher gives directions, teacher demonstrates, and teacher praises and encourages*. It is noted that under teacher lectures, the teacher engages the students using PowerPoint presentations and slides, using stories and narratives, using creative communications techniques like music, art, songs, video clips, and using actual activities. Here,

the students become attentive to the lecture as they listen and participate in the discussion. This kind of engagement is considered as *cognitive engagement* where the students are required to comprehend concepts and acquire skills, process information, and solve challenging problems. The teacher transmits knowledge and skills, and the students have to become interested in the lesson to participate in the class discussion. It is important that teachers have a good repertoire of teaching strategies to keep the students engaged and not get bored in the process (Teaching Commons, 2010).

Matrix 3. Teaching and Learning Engagements observed during the online class observations

Teaching Engagement Observed	Student Engagement Observed	Implications for engagement
<p>1. Teacher lectures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture engaging in PowerPoint Presentation • Lecture engaging in stories/narratives • Lecture engaging in songs, music and art • Lecture engaging in activities 	<p>Students listen & participate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students attentive to the lecture • Students listen and pay close attention • students participate when teacher asks them about the lecture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive engagement aimed at comprehending complex concepts and acquiring skills. It conveys processing of information whereby students gain a critical or higher-order understanding of the subject matter and solve challenging problems. • Teaching is transmitting information. There is transfer of learning. • Students have to get interested in the content of their lesson and participate in the discussion • There is a need for varied teaching strategies to maximize engagement of students
<p>2. Teacher asks questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking solicitous questions • Asking LOTS questions • Asking HOTS questions • Asking Feedback 	<p>Student Talk-response</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • verbal response to LOTS questions • verbal response to HOTS questions • student-talk initiation • students present reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral engagement conveys the presence of "on-task behavior." This entails effort and persistence along with paying attention, asking questions, seeking help that enables one to accomplish the task at hand, and not disrupting instruction. • Teaching is developing and harnessing the students' mind <p>Students have to be engaged in the class discussion and participate actively in the Q&A</p>

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<p>3. Teacher gives directions</p>	<p>Students following instructions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral engagement is the observable act of students being involved in learning • Teacher empowering students to work independently • Students learn to cooperate and collaborate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving instructions on what to do • Giving assignment/activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students work on seatwork • students work on assignments 	
<p>4. Teacher demonstrates</p>	<p>Students work on activity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral engagement is the observable act of students being involved in learning • Teacher allowing students to develop skills & solve real-life problems • Learning through knowledge application
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrating what to do • Demonstrating how to do the activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • student's individual work activity • students cooperative group work activity 	
<p>5. Teacher praises/encourages</p>	<p>Students' motivation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This demonstrates affective/emotional engagement • Teaching is developing students' mind to better appreciate learning and develop core values • Students develop social graces and become appreciative of their learning and schooling. • The greater the student's interest level, enjoyment, positive attitude, positive value held, curiosity, and a sense of belonging (and the less the anxiety, sadness, stress, and boredom), the greater the <i>affective</i> engagement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving praises for responding • Giving motivation to work on the activity • Acknowledging students' presence, response, work, etc. • Congratulating the students • Thanking the class 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students are motivated and synergized • Teachers and students exhibit good vibes • Students get inspired and become participative 	

Engaging students when the teacher asks questions activates the students by asking solicitous questions (*e.g. asking if the students understand; if the students have questions*); asking lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) questions, and higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) questions. The students are provided the time for student-talk responses to LOTS and HOTS questions. There are instances when students initiate the response and there are situations where the teacher requires the students to do the reporting of a topic assigned to them. This kind of engagement is *behavioral engagement* as it conveys the presence of “on-task behavior”. This entails effort and persistence along with paying attention, asking questions, seeking help that enables one to accomplish the task at hand, and not disrupting instructions. Teaching here is developing and harnessing the students’ mind, such that they are actively engaged in the class discussion and in responding to questions.

Engaging the students when the *teacher gives directions* encourages the students to work on seatwork and activities, and allows them to work on their assignments. Again, this is a *behavioral*

engagement as students are observed to work independently, and collaborate with their peers. *Teacher demonstrates* is another way of engaging the students, as they allow the students to develop skills and solve real-life problems. Learning is through knowledge application. This also manifests a *behavioral* type of engagement.

Teacher praises/encourages also engages the students to participate in the lesson especially in online teaching. Teachers usually acknowledge the attendance of their students. They praise and congratulate the students when they respond to their questions. They thank the students for their presence and participation and encourage them to do their activities. These actuations from the teachers motivate and synergize the students, inspiring them to participate in the class discussion and activities. This kind of engagement is considered as *affective/emotional* since teaching develops student's mind to better appreciate learning and develop core values. The students indirectly develop social graces and become appreciative of their learning and schooling. There is greater interest and enjoyment on the part of the learners, developing positive attitude and values. These are very essential for emotional development especially this time of the pandemic when many students experience anxiety, stress and boredom.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The transition brought about by the new modality of classroom delivery had forced schools to hold classes virtually. The School of Education college instructors at San Isidro College has to embrace the new way of teaching, just as the dean also has to observe classes the virtual way, using the evaluation form suggested by the accrediting agency. Re-creating the traditional classroom to remote online classroom has made instructors creative in their teaching practices and strategies. The instructors' efforts highlighted the importance of student-teacher relationships as well as student-to-student relationship. Simple practices like greeting students, showing appreciation, giving praises and acknowledgements, and being authentic help to build these relationships. College instructors have re-created a new model of teaching strategy utilizing varied presentations and teaching styles; allowing small-group student learning structures that support collaborative learning; and engaging students to participate and become involve in learning despite their being remote. These remote learning innovations reveal the power of the teacher's imagination when adapting to change.

Still, SIC needs more technical preparedness with necessary online educational resources for both teachers and students. There is a need for proficient computer knowledge, communication skills, innovative online teaching techniques, and skills to deal with the demands of online platforms. Virtual classroom management requires patience, empathy, and care for the students, proper handling of teaching-learning tools, and additional technical skills to manage online teaching process. Free access to e-books and e-journals, open educational resources, institutional as well as personal internet connections, Wi-fi, access to a free account on Zoom & Google Meet are found as relevant tools for online class and virtual learning.

The findings of this study revealed that the SED college instructors *excellently* pursued the teaching strategies they deemed to enhance students' engagement in the lesson and activities they prepared. The teachers innovatively figure out how they could apply the teaching strategies they have learned, practiced, and researched on. Teaching and learning engagement of the teacher and the students are identified as cognitive, behavioral and affective. These are evidently manifested

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when teacher gives lectures, teacher asks questions, teacher gives directions, teacher demonstrates, and teacher praises/encourages. Succinctly, observation of classes online shows promises of a new hybrid model of teaching strategy and engagements in the academe.

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